

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine

VOLUME 2

ISSUE 21 APRIL-JUNE ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

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A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume II, Issue II | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

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“SAVING, SPENDING, AND SURVIVING: THE POWER OF FINANCIAL LITERACY”

Most individuals save money and have bank accounts. But why still many individuals don't have bank accounts? Many of the reasons are lack of money, no need for them to open bank account because it is just enough to spend for their daily living, the bank is far from their residence, cannot provide bank requirements for them to be able to open an account, or the maintaining balance is very high.

Many individuals are more likely to practice informal methods of savings like piggy bank or coin jar saving as the simplest way of saving money. Another is the “paluwagan” (rotating savings group) where group of people contribute a fixed amount of money in a monthly basis and one member receives the total collected money at the end of the month. Keeping money at home usually they placed it in an envelope, they put money inside the cabinet, or hidden part of the house instead of depositing in a bank. Some individuals lend their extra money to friends, relatives, and neighbors with a minimum interest, then saved the returned borrowed money. Instead of saving money, they invest in livestock that can be sold later to have cash.

How an individual spending their money? Most of them spend on basic needs like foods, housing, education of children, utilities, transportation, payment of debts, medicine maintenance, and others spending for their wants. Many individuals buy in small quantities instead of in bulk this is to stretch their monthly budget specially the prices of essential needs are fluctuating and purchasing power becomes low because of this they also consider prices in their buying decisions. They usually choose products with discounts and promos to stretch their budget like “buy one, take one”. Other also buy in bulk especially items with long shelf life. Due to inflation and uncertainty which we are experiencing right now, many individuals reduce spending on dining out, other forms of entertainment, buying luxury items, and cancelling scheduled trips due to unforeseen current events. Despite limited budget, many individuals buying healthy foods showing of health awareness to support overall well-being and helping to prevent diseases.

Other reason for spending is relaxation due to stress. It provides enjoyment and promoting well-being as it supports mental and emotional health if an individual is experiencing burn-out. Another way that individuals spending is on gadgets, trending products and services and social activities. Before spending, individuals need careful budgeting to avoid purchasing unnecessary things. It ensures that income is exactly allocated to cover essential needs of family, savings, and even wants. Others already practicing budgeting and they plan before purchase and only buy what are essentials. Eliminating vices like smoking, excessive consumption of alcohols, gambling, and even impulsive buying frees up money that can be used for essential

needs. Budgeting before spending is very important and to avoid debt ensuring that every peso has a purpose, especially for individual with limited income to become financially resilience.

When we talk about surviving financially, it goes beyond spending habits. Many individuals adjust their spending behavior and lifestyle to cope with fluctuations. Some taking sidelines as additional source of income like online selling, driving, cooking, or freelancing. Being resourcefulness and flexibility in earning money is a positive sign of being resilience in times of difficulties. Many individuals manage their money in a daily basis prioritizing daily need. Strong family ties are another way for survival mechanism like borrowing from relatives and friends. If a family is usually going out for dinner, it would be preferred to cooking at home instead of eating in a restaurant. Reducing electricity and water consumption. Working abroad is also a survival strategy to send money home to support their families.

Financial literacy gives a person the confidence to manage and spend their income wisely and direct where money should go. Individuals who are financially literate understand the importance of saving regularly which leads to financial stability. Financial literacy opens the door to wealth-building opportunities. Instead of just earning money, they learn how to make money for them. With the right knowledge of financial literacy individuals rely less on others for financial support that leads to freedom and independence.

Finally, financial literacy is the ability of knowing how your money works for you, including earning, budgeting, spending, saving, and investing. Your ability to manage your debt. Preparing for emergencies, education of children, retirement, and other long-term financial goals. Financial literacy is not just about the amount of money – it is a special ability that builds resilience, independence, and the ability to secure for a better future.

